

Importance of Yoga, Pranayama, Suryanamaskara Meditation in Life, and components of Stress- Free Life

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Abstract:

Yoga is a spiritual discipline based on an extremely subtle science which focuses on bringing harmony between mind and body. Yoga is a mind and body practice that build strength and flexibility which help in managing pain and reducing stress. The word yoga is derived from the Sanskrit root 'yuj' meaning 'to 'join' or to yoke or to unite. There are various styles of yoga combining physical postures, breathing techniques and meditation. Pranayama is the yogic practice of focussing on breath. Suryanamaskara is yogic practice of physical postures consisting a series of 12 physical postures. Yoga practice in day-to-day life of each and every individual. The present paper is concerned with the benefits of yoga as a component of stress-free life. The paper will also highlight on the importance of Pranayama, Surya namaskar and Meditation in life. The paper will also highlight on the practice of yoga to enhance the physical and mental wellbeing of an individual. The research is carried out on the existing facts and literature available in this area of study so far. The findings of the research show that opportunities are increasing for Yoga as a component for a stress-free life.

Keywords: yoga, pranayama, suryanamaskara, meditation, stress-free.

Introduction:

Yoga is a system of spiritual and ascetic discipline to develop or improve one's inherent power in a balanced manner. Yoga helps in reducing stress because it promotes relaxation, which is the natural opposite of stress. Yoga can benefit three aspects of ourselves that are often affected by stress: our body, mind, and

breathing. The word 'yoga' is derived from the Sanskrit root 'YUJ' meaning to join or to yoke or to unite. It offers the means to attain complete self-realization. Yoga is a system of physical postures, breathing techniques and sometimes meditation derived from yoga but it is often practiced independently especially in western culture to promote physical and emotional wellbeing. According to Oxford Dictionary Yoga is a Hindu spiritual and ascetic discipline, a part of which including breath control, simple meditation, and the adaptation of specific bodily postures, is widely practised for health and relaxation. Yoga aids in controlling a person's body, mind, and soul. It brings the physical and mental discipline together to soothe the body and mind. It also aids in managing stress and anxiety and keeps you relaxed. Yoga asana is known to develop Vigor, flexibility, and confidence.

A brief history and development of yoga:

The practice of yoga is believed to have started with the very dawn of civilization. The science of yoga has its origin thousands of years ago long before the first religion or belief systems were born. Tentatively, the classical period between 500 BC-800 AD is considered as the classical period which is also considered as the most fertile and prominent period in the history and development of yoga. The period between 800 AD-1700AD as the post classical period and the period between 1700-1900 is considered as the modern period of development of Yoga. Though Yoga was being practiced in the pre-Vedic period, the great Sage Maharshi Patanjali systematized and codified the then existing practices of Yoga, its meaning and its related knowledge through his Yoga Sutras. Yoga originated in ancient India over 5,000 years ago as a philosophical and spiritual practice. It was a significant aspect of several Indian philosophical systems, including Hinduism, Buddhism, and Jainism, where it was used to promote spiritual growth and understanding.

Modern yoga is a wide range of yoga practices with differing purposes, encompassing in its various form's yoga philosophy derived from the Vedas, physical postures derived from Hatha yoga, devotional and tantra-based practices, and Hindu nation-building approaches.

Objectives of the study:

- To study the importance of yoga in our day-to-day life.
- To study the benefits of practising yoga to enhance the physical, mental and wellbeing of an individual.
- To highlight on the importance of Pranayama, Surya namaskar and Meditation in life

Methodology:

For the purpose of the research study secondary sources of literary information such as text books on yoga, books on contemporary yoga practices, articles on yoga, websites ets is used.

The importance of Pranayama, Suryanamaskara and meditation in life and components of stress-free life:

Yoga is a way of life or Art of living through mental, spiritual and physical path. It allows to achieve stillness and to tap into the consciousness of inner self. It also helps in learning how to rise above the pull of mind, emotions and lower bodily needs and face challenges of day-to-day life. Yoga is an ancient practice that has been used for centuries to promote physical and mental well-being. One of the main benefits of yoga is its ability to reduce stress and anxiety. In today's fast-paced world, stress and anxiety are becoming increasingly common, making yoga an essential tool for maintaining mental and emotional health. When we experience stress, our bodies release cortisol, a hormone that can cause physical and emotional symptoms such as tension, headaches, and irritability. Yoga can help to reduce the production of cortisol and promote the release of endorphins, which are natural mood-boosters. This makes yoga an effective tool for managing stress and anxiety.

One of the ways yoga helps to reduce stress and anxiety is through its focus on breathing. Pranayama, or the practice of controlled breathing, is a key component of yoga. The deep, slow breathing that is practiced during yoga can help to calm the mind and reduce feelings of stress and anxiety.

Yoga also helps to reduce stress and anxiety by promoting relaxation. The slow and steady movements of yoga, combined with the focus on the breath, help to relax the body and mind. Many yoga poses, such as forward bends and twists, are particularly effective at releasing tension and stress from the body.

Pranayama:

Pranayama is the yogic practice of focusing on breath. Prana means “vital life force” and Yama means to gain control. In yoga, breath is associated with the prana, thus, pranayama means to elevate the prana shakti, or lifer energies. Pranayama is the ancient practice of controlling the timing, duration and frequency of every breath and hold. The goal of pranayama is to connect your body and mind.

Types of Pranayama:

- Quiet Breathing
- Deep Breathing
- Fast Breathing
- Tri bandha and Pranayama
- Nadi Shuddhi Pranayama (Alternate nostril breathing-1)
- Anuloma-Viloma (Alternate nostril breathing -2)
- Suryan Bhedan Pranayama (Right nostril breathing)

Pranayama helps in promoting healthy and high-quality sleep, It also helps to lower the stress level by normalizing our mood and lowering the stress level. Pranayama aims to bring harmony and build a connection between the breath, mind and body. This practice removes toxins, supplies the body with oxygen, improves the quality of breath, increases lung capacity, minimize stress and anxiety.

Surya namaskar:

Surya Namaskar, salute to the sun or sun salutation is a practice in yoga as incorporating a flow sequence of some twelve gracefully linked asanas. Surya namaskar is a Sanskrit word which means salute to the sun. Regular practice of Surya namaskar ensures proper and efficient functioning of not only the muscles and joints of the body but also stimulates the internal organs. Especially the stomach and other abdominal organs as it involves alternative stretching and compression at the abdominal area. This routine is generally considered to be a morning practice which is to be performed at dawn. The sequence of asanas or poses stimulates all organs, systems, muscles and chakras. Among other health benefits of Surya Namaskar, it is also said to cultivate stillness and concentration of the mind.

Benefits of Surya Namaskar

- Warms Up Your Whole Body
- Raises Your Heart Rate
- Tones Muscles
- Improves Flexibility
- Boosts Your Immune System
- Motivates You to Practice
- Integrates Breath and Movement
- Reduces Stress and Anxiety.

MEDITATION:

Meditation is a practice where an individual, trains the mind or induces a mode of consciousness, either to realize some benefits or for the mind to simply acknowledge its contents without becoming identified with that content. The term meditation refers to a broad variety of practices that includes techniques designed to provide relaxation, built energy or life force and develop compassions.

Conclusion

Now-a-days, millions and millions of people across the globe have benefitted by the practice of Yoga which has been preserved and promoted by the great eminent Yoga Masters from ancient time to this date. The practice of Yoga is blossoming, and growing more vibrant every day. Yoga also helps to reduce stress and anxiety by promoting

mindfulness. The practice of yoga encourages you to focus on the present moment, which can help to reduce feelings of worry and anxiety. This mindfulness can also help to improve overall mental and emotional well-being.

In addition to these benefits, yoga can also help to improve sleep, boost the immune system, and improve overall physical health. It can also be a great way to improve overall flexibility and balance.

Yoga is an effective tool for managing stress and anxiety, as it promotes relaxation, mindfulness, and deep breathing. Incorporating a regular yoga practice into your life can help to reduce feelings of stress and anxiety and improve overall mental and emotional well-being.

REFERENCES

1. Swami Sivananda, Sri. Yoga in daily Life. A divine Life Society Publication,1999
2. Claire, T. Yoga for Men. Posters for Healthy stress-free living. The Career Press, In.U.S. A, 2004
3. Paramhans, Swami Maheshwar Ananda, Yoga in Daily life. The System. Ibera,2005
4. Ananda, Sri, The Complete Book of Yoga. Harmony of Body and Mind, Orient paperbacks, 2023, Delhi.
5. <https://www.researchgate.net>>
6. <https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in>>
7. en. Wikipedia. Organ./wiki/Three-Yoga